

Investigation and preparation of PDC glass/ceramic coatings applied to different pre-treated stainless steel AISI441 substrates

M. Parchovianský¹, I. Parchovianská², P. Švančárek³, D. Galusek³, G. Motz⁴,

¹ Department of Coating Processes, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

(E-mail: milan.parchoviansky@tnuni.sk)

² Department of Functional Materials, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

³ Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChFT STU, FunGlass, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

⁴ University of Bayreuth, Ceramic Materials Engineering, D-95440 Bayreuth, Germany

ABSTRACT

This study describes the investigation of different cleaning procedures on AISI 441 stainless steel substrates and preparation of coatings containing passive ceramic and commercial glass fillers. In order to achieve well adherent coatings without failures, stainless steel substrates were cleaned by four different cleaning procedures. The prepared slurry was then deposited onto the steel substrate via spray coating. The experimental conditions for the pre-treatment of stainless steel are shown in Tab.1.

Tab.1: Experimental conditions of pre-treatment of stainless steel

Shorcut	Pre-treatment of stainless steel
U	3-steps ultrasonic vibration cleaning in acetone, ethanol and deionized water (10 min)
S	Sandblasting with glass beads (70-110 μ m), ultrasonic cleaning
K	Chemical etching – Kroll's reagent (distilled water, HNO ₃ , HF), 20 s
S+K	Sandblasting with glass beads + etching with Kroll's reagent

The bond coat was prepared from the commercial polymer Durazane 2250 (Merck KGaA, Germany) by the dip-coating method (dip-coater RDC 15, Relamatic, Switzerland). The pyrolysis of the bond-coat was carried out in air (Nabertherm® N41/H, Nabertherm, Germany) at a temperature of 450 °C for 1 h. The top coats were prepared from the commercial polymer – Durazane 1800 (Merck KGaA, Germany), passive fillers and commercial glass. The passive fillers used were ZrO₂ stabilized with 8 mol. % Y₂O₃ (8YSZ, Inframat, USA), AYZ powder and commercial glass (G018-281, Schott AG). Two compositions of top coat were prepared, C2c and D2. The prepared compositions are listed in Tab.2.

Tab.2: Compositions of the composite top coats after pyrolysis (vol. %)

Sample name	Durazane1800	8YSZ	AYZ	G018-281
C2c	30	35	-	35
D2	25	20	20	35

The SEM cross-sectional micrographs of compositions C2c and D2 in Fig.1 show the bonding between the bond coat and the steel substrate treated by different cleaning procedures. After pyrolysis of the coatings at 850 °C irrespective of the cleaning process applied, the bond coat did not delaminate from the steel surface, indicating its good adhesion to the metal substrate. An intact bond coat approximately 1 μ m thick was observed in all cases. The top coat layers of both studied compositions, C2c and D2, were almost dense, with only small closed pores observed.

Fig. 1: SEM cross-section of pyrolysed C2c and D2 coatings. The applied cleaning procedure is indicated by the abbreviation in the upper right corner of each figure.

SEM cross-sections of C2c and D2 compositions after corrosion tests are shown in Fig.2. In all cases, except for ultrasonic cleaning, during the corrosion tests the bond coat delaminated from the surface of stainless steel. Chemical etching of the steel surface with the Kroll's solution probably caused changes in the microstructure and chemical composition of the steel, resulting in peeling of the coating. For samples with a sandblasted surface treatment, or a combination of sandblasting and etching, the bond coat and the top coat were detached because of the high surface roughness, although it was assumed that such a surface treatment would lead to the highest adhesion. Simple cleaning by ultrasonication in acetone, ethanol and deionised water is the most effective way for achieving a sufficient bonding of the bond coat to the steel substrate after corrosion tests.

Fig. 2: SEM cross-section of C2c and D2 compositions after corrosion tests. The applied cleaning procedure is indicated by the abbreviation in the upper right corner of each figure

Keywords: Polymer derived ceramics, bond coat, passive fillers, corrosion

Acknowledgment:

Financial support of this work by the APVV 0014-15 grant and the Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst (DAAD) grant scheme is gratefully acknowledged. This paper was also created in the frame of the project Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass (CEGLASS), ITMS code is 313011R453, operational program Research and innovation, co-funded from European Regional Development Fund.